

TEACHING METHODS USED TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING

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Annotation: This article deals with information about creative thinking, its importance in modern education for students. On the other hand, ways of developing creative thinking in learners were noted. Innovative methods and games according to the theme that can be utilized in classroom were highlighted.

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As education changes all the time, the focus on memorization is slowly giving way to a more all-around method that encourages creative thinking. To put it simply, creative thinking means being able to see problems and events in new ways and come up with new ways to solve them. It's what sparks inventions, moves society forward, and helps people grow as people. As we move further into the 21st century, it's no longer just nice to be able to think freely; it's necessary. Creativity is one of the most appreciated learning skills current the XXI century. Creativity is conceived as a higher-order thinking skill based on complex and postformal thought concerned with the creation of new and valuable ideas. Higher-order thinking skills are those involved in proficient and strategic thought, and these skills comprise critical, creative and metacognitive thinking, also known as deep learning. In addition, the development of creativity is today considered essential in order to achieve an effective and a high-level learning[1]. The ability to think creatively is an important skill students need to develop as they grow older. It is an ability that not only encourages one to think creatively but also enables one to generate fresh concepts and find original solutions to issues. It is

imperative to develop creative thinking skills among students to build a community of change-makers. It helps students to outshine others in a competition through their creative solutions. This article discusses the importance of creative thinking in students and the activities that can be organized in schools to improve the creative thinking skills of students.

In order to further increase students' interest in geography lessons, it is desirable to organize lessons in an interesting way. Some teachers complain that students are not interested in classes and spend more time in front of the phone and computer. One thinks that the reason for this is that the teachers are not able to organize the lessons in an interesting way. " GEOGRAPHY RIDDLES ", " WHO TELLS A LOT OF INFORMATION?", " WHAT FOR? ", " WHEN THE NUMBERS ARE TALKING ", "DO NOT BE LEFT BEHIND", "AN INTELLIGENT STUDENT, "CONNECTIG SUBJECT INFORMATION WITH LIFE", "FIND YOUR PLACE" methods. The first method. Taking into account the specific characteristics of the teaching classe s, using the following geography riddles in the form of problematic situations in order to attract attention and interest in the lesson at the beginning of the lesson or in the process of working in groups - by dividing them into two groups and giving riddles to the groups in turn, giving them five seconds to think, 5-, 6-, 7-, 8-, 9- and 10 in the form of handouts The efficiency of the lessons would be higher if different methods were used in the first grade taking into account the age characteristics of the students.

Developing creative thinking in learners has long been considered an essential aspect of education and brain development. Harold Bloom (1956), the American Literary critic and educator, devised his Bloom's Taxonomy which categorises learning into 6 categories—the final stage is to "create." Bloom asserts that creation is an indispensable part of learning in which students are allowed to produce their own unique work, investigate solutions to problems, design a product, or develop a theory. Therefore, it can be said that creative

thinking for students forms the culmination of students' knowledge and education.

Importance of creative thinking skills[2]:

- It aids students in solving challenging issues or difficulties that may arise.
- It improves the productivity of students and encourages them to work with more enthusiasm.
- If students are working in a team, it builds collaboration between the team.
- It motivates students to think outside the box and hence gives them the freedom to experiment and come up with innovative ideas.
- Creative thinking skills help students to develop problem-solving skills, which is an essential skill required to thrive in their academic and professional lives.

As we see above, creative thinking abilities play significant role in modern education. We can create and develop our pupils thinking abilities by using some strategies to develop creative thinking skills. One of the many strategies that can help students develop their writing ability is the essay. While essay writing is a great opportunity for students to practice their critical and creative thinking skills, there are always those who are looking for easy ways out. As a result, students have more opportunities to complete their academic work and meet high requirements. This opens up additional opportunities for students in solving academic tasks and helps them achieve high standards. The ability to think creatively is fundamental in all walks of life and is not limited to the arts. The hidden ingredient that leads to breakthroughs and inventions, whether it's solving complicated mathematical problems or designing a marketing plan, is imagination. Students who are able to think creatively are better able to succeed in a world where change is the only constant.

Getting out of your comfort zone and taking risks are often part of being creative. Trying new things and failing sometimes is what it's all about. But in a

regular school setting, failure is often seen as a bad thing. To help people become creative thinkers, we need to change this way of thinking and see failure as an important part of the learning process. Tell your kids that it's okay to make mistakes as long as they learn from them and keep trying. Setting up a setting that encourages curiosity and questioning is one of the first things that can help people think creatively. What makes the sky change color when the sun goes down? If cars could fly, what would happen? There are no stupid questions, and every question is a way to find new ways to be creative. By encouraging students to be curious, teachers can help them build a mind-set that is open to new experiences and questions what they think they know[3].

Painting, music, and theater aren't just fun things to do after school; they're also great ways to improve your ability to think creatively. Art activities give kids a way to express themselves, learn about other points of view, and make new relationships. Adding creative tasks to classes like math and physics can help students think creatively. In the digital age we live in now, technology opens up a world of artistic expression and new ideas. Adding technology to the school curriculum can give students the tools they need to make their creative ideas come to life. For example, students can learn how to code, make apps, tell digital stories, and make videos.

A key aspect of creative thinking is the ability to see challenges not as obstacles but as opportunities. Cultivating a growth mindset in students — where challenges are embraced, and effort is seen as the path to mastery — can significantly enhance their creative capabilities. Encourage students to view problems as puzzles to be solved, and remind them that every challenge is an opportunity to learn and grow. Below are some methods, exercises and activities that teachers and schools can make use of for developing students' creative thinking skills in the classroom or even beyond the school[4].

a) Creative Thinking Games For Students

- **Dictionary story**

This exercise can be quite beneficial for teachers who like to pique students' interest in vocabulary and enrich their skills. So get yourself a dictionary, pick a random word, and try to make up a brief story using the word you chose, the word above it, and the word below it. This exercise will reveal your students' potential to find connections between words and mix ideas that might not relate to each other at first glance. Ultimately, your students would have crafted a narrative out of simple means. This can form the basis of your fiction writing lessons and help your students when they are stuck for ideas.

- **Six-word story**

When teachers are at a loss for creative thinking exercises for students, they like to resort to the old-fashioned technique called "six-word story." It basically tests the students' ability to be creative using only six words to form a story. According to Doug Weller, three elements make up a good six-word story: it makes sense to the reader, it takes him/her on a journey, and it leaves the reader with emotion. A perfect example of this would be Hemingway's famous "*For sale: baby shoes. Never worn.*" Make sure to give this exercise to your students next lesson and watch their creative minds bloom!

- **Avoid the letter 'e'**

Henri Matisse, the French Visual Artist, says "Don't wait for inspiration. It comes while working." Recent research has debunked the myth that creativity is inherent or genetic. On the contrary, scientists now believe that creativity is a skill that is acquired through regular practice and exercise. An entertaining way to develop your students' creative thinking skills is to play the game "avoid the letter e." You can organize the class into pairs and allow them to have a conversation without using the letter 'e'.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that creative thinking

skills are essential for students to excel in their academics and also in their careers. You can organize these activities in your classroom for improving the creative thinking skills of your students. As was already established, students need creative thinking skills to excel in a myriad of endeavors throughout their lives. There is a consensus among scholars that creativity is not just another skill, but rather a complex process of human subjectivity that is based on a set of psychological resources that are specifically configured and regulate human behavior. Contemporary researchers have expanded the concept of creativity by recognizing that creative action is a dynamic and inconclusive process and is even co-constitute with the broader social context. Considering the different approaches to their study assumed by Rodhes, creativity has been defined as a result, as a process, as a construct derived from the influence of the context and as a personality feature of human nature.

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